

RESPONSE PAPER

LAST NAME: GONO

FIRST NAME: CHARLES

PROGRAM CODE : DILT

COURSE CODE : ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: PERIOD 1

INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

ESSAY WRITING-THE BASICS

1) INTRODUCTION

In Response Paper 1 (RP1), I began the study important subject of Essay Writing. The study was organized under the topic, Essay Writing, The Basics written by The Learning Centre, of the University of New South Wales. According to the writer, a good academic essay should answer a question or task that aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence. It should include relevant examples, supporting evidence and information from academic texts or credible sources (EUCLID 2015, 2).

When starting an essay, it is important to choose US or UK English for spelling, punctuation rules and formatting of references. An essay must be started as early as possible to give yourself enough time to read, research, think and write. An academic essay follows a list of basic steps which is in no strict order. For example, analyze the question and define key terms, establish a possible thesis, research the topic using credible academic sources for support and evidence, take note from the readings, write an essay plan and organize your ideas, write the first draft of the essay, edit and redraft your essay, have a friend or colleague read it, check your references and bibliography, and final draft completed and hand it in as shown in the Basic Steps in Writing an Essay Learning Centre Guide (ibid.).

2) STARTING THE ESSAY

Essay writing is not a linear process and should be started as early as possible to give yourself enough time to read, research, think and write. The key requirements in

starting an essay are defining the questions, analyzing the task, and answering the essay question. It is important to understand exactly what the question requires you to do. In essay writing, identifying the key words and clarifying the approach you are require taking will determine a successful essay (ibid.).

In starting an essay, the writer needs to construct an initial plan which is your initial response to the topic or question. You need to research, question your response and find some answers. The initial essay plan will enable you to work out your initial thoughts and ideas about the topic and write a preliminary essay plan to help guide your research. It also helps you work out how you will answer the question, which information you will use and structuring an essay as shown in The Learning Centre Guide Essay & Assignment Planning (ibid.).

a) Researching the topic

Researching is about following a line of investigation into the topic to draw on the work of other writers and researchers. Therefore, reading and researching are very important to essay writing. Researching provides the knowledge and evidence that allows you to reference, cite and develop a thesis and argument to answer the essay question (EUCLID 2015, 3).

Researching is time consuming, therefore, to start reading early with a purpose will provide plenty of time to familiarize yourself with the topic and develop your ideas. The questions that need to be answered when writing an essay are what I know about the topic, the research required to answer the essay question and the materials needed to support the answer.

The purpose of research is to gather sources of information for referencing and citation. Therefore, take note of bibliographic details including the author, date, title, publisher and place of publication: or journal articles, include volume and issue number as shown in The Learning Centre Guide Effective Notetaking from written text (ibid.).

b) Organizing your ideas

The information gathered through research and ideas should be organized to answer the essay question and how the essay should be structured using both creative and critical thinking. Critical thinking is vital because it encouraged you to barrow the focus or scope of your ideas and also broaden your ideas,(ibid.). A second essay plan should be drawn up base on research and note taken to decide possible answer to the question, information you will use to answer the question, example to provide evidence to support your answer, decide which points you will discuss and in which order, and write them in point form as your essay plan.

Quotation marks should be used when you use words from a source, and either use the exact words with quotation marks or restate the point in your own words. Use quotation when there is especially strong language in the quote that emphasizes the meaning very

well and when an authority figure says something that can help you persuade the reader. Use long quotation when the quotations are over four line. They will be indented and look like a separate little paragraph (EUCLID 2015, 7).

An essay should include a range of information and viewpoints from different authors that explore the key arguments and relevant aspects of a particular topic. Diverse views should be included, don't include only evidence that support what you are arguing, if there are opposing views then they need to be examined to explain why one argument is more convincing than another and how they relate to the conclusion your essay arrives at. Paraphrase information and ideas that an author has produced on a topic. The paraphrase must look very different than how the author originally wrote it and it must be your words. The information that you are providing must be an accurate representation of what the author originally wrote and must cite the work the information came from (EUCLID 2015, 3, 8).

i) *Writing the essay*

When writing an essay, state the main thesis of your paper at the beginning in the opening paragraph and write clearly by writing short sentences. The writing should focus readers' attention on the main ideas you wish to express, not on the words you have chosen to express those ideas (EUCLID 2015, 43). It is important to choose US or UK English for spelling, punctuation rules and formatting of references and be consistent. Write in a formal academic style by using logical connectors so that there is flow in the essay. Avoid contraction such as can't, won't, isn't etc. (EUCLID 2015, 39).

Abbreviations should be used only in contexts where they are clear to readers, and never begin a sentence with a lower-case abbreviation. Begin a sentence with an acronym only if there is no reasonable way to rewrite it. An acronym must be introduced when first used in a text by placing the acronym or its source phrase in parentheses and thereafter using just the acronym (EUCLID 2015, 66). It is important to save your file with proper name format and always run spell check on your work. An essay writer should avoid plagiarism. When you use the word of a source, use quotation marks. Moreover, you should not present a close paraphrase from a source: either use the exact words with quotation marks or restate the point in your own words (EUCLAD 2015, 8, 43, 44).

Writing an essay starts with the first draft of all the information gathered during the research and help work out the structure and framework of your essay. The first draft will help to determine how to answer the question and which evidence and examples you will use to support your argument. The essay question should be kept in mind as you draft, edit and work out your argument. The draft will be refined through editing and redrafting. The structure of an essay includes an introduction, body and conclusion that communicate your idea and answer the question. The introduction of an essay starts from general to specific by introducing the topic, answer the question with a thesis statement and provide a summary by mentioning all the main ideas. The main thesis of the essay should be stated in the opening paragraph (EUCLID 2015, 4, 44).

The body of the essay consists of paragraphs which is the building block in the construction of your argument. The body answer the question, show knowledge gap of material read, offer exposition and evidence to develop your argument and used relevant examples and authorities quotes. The conclusion moves from specific to general by restating your answer to the question, re-summarises the main points and include a final broad statement. In the conclusion you round off by summing up the essay. After the first draft, putting the essay away for few days allows you to consider your essay with fresh eyes. The final draft should be carefully proofread, checking spelling and punctuation (EUCLID 2015, 19).

ii) Referencing the essay

Referencing is important in order to guide against plagiarism, a serious academic offence that can have serious consequences. Plagiarism is using a source of information without giving credit to the author of the source of information. In order to avoid plagiarism, the author must be properly cited or source that has provided the information (EUCLID 2015, 13). All academic essays must contain references which show the sources of information. Referencing allows you to acknowledge the contribution of other writer and researchers in your work. Citations are not used simply to avoid plagiarism; they have other important roles. The methods of citations are in-text citation and list of work cited. However, we cannot cite everything, when the information you are writing about is common knowledge that can be found in numerous areas (EUCLID 2015, 30).

Referencing is also a way to give credit to the writer from whom you have borrowed words and ideas. The usage of citation of a particular scholar means you acknowledge and respect the intellectual property rights of that researcher, The Learning Centre guides on plagiarism and on various citation styles (EUCLID 2015, 5, 8).

Referencing is a way to provide evidence to support the assertions and claims in your own assignments. Referencing should always be accurate, allowing your reader to trace the sources of information you have used. The best way to make sure you reference accurately is to keep a record of all the sources such as quote, paraphrase, statistic / data or visual that is borrowed from another source when reading and researching for an assignment. referencing makes an essay more persuasive. You need to reference information from books and journal articles, newspapers and magazines, pamphlets or brochures, films, documentaries, television programs or advertisements, websites or electronic resources, letters, emails, online discussion forums, personal interview printed diagrams, illustration, charts or pictures (EUCLID 2015, 12).

iii) Editing the essay

One of the vital aspects of writing an essay is editing, because it brings the best out of writing and dramatically improve it. Once you have a well-organized and fairly complete draft, the editing should take the following into consideration as stated in EUCLID (2015, 5):

- Check the overall structure of your essay; does it have a clear introduction, body and conclusion?
- Make sure that each paragraph has a clear main point that relates to the argument.
- Make sure that the paragraphs are arranged in logical sequence.
- Revise sentences, and make sure the words you use mean what you think they mean. Check punctuation and spelling. A good dictionary is a useful tool.
- Check transition signals. Be sure that a reader can follow the sequence of ideas from sentence to sentence and from paragraph to paragraph.

In addition, it is recommended that the writer answer the following questions when editing the essay:

- Have I answer the question as directly and comprehensively as possible?
- Does the argument make sense? Is it balanced and well researched?
- Is the evidence relevant to and supportive to my argument?
- Have I used a consistent citation style? Have I referenced all my quotes and paragraphs?
- If there were any special instructions or guidelines for this assignment, have I followed them?
- Have I remained within the set word limit?

iv) Handing the essay in

After editing an essay before handing it in, the writer must read the assignment guidelines for the course and follow them. When the essay is finished, read it to ensure it sound right. Writing that does not sound right will not read right (EUCLID 2015, 44).

Find out how the lecturer / tutor would like assignment presented and make sure you comply with their requirements. The essay is not completed until it is handed in. it's important for the writer to make sure the date the assignment is due, where and to whom the assignment should be submitted. If cover sheet is required, find out where to obtain it. Ensure the essay is formatted correctly and print on one side of the page only. Staple the essay in the top left-hand corner and keep an extra copy for yourself (EUCLID 2015, 5)

3) CONCLUSION

The ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSEPACK PERIOD 1 covered Essay Writing, The Basics which includes starting the essay, researching the topic, organizing your ideas, writing the essay, referencing the essay and editing the essay. It further discussed fundamentals of formatting punctuation, and grammar that are vital for effective communication and research purposes. The coursepack also explained the differences between US and UK spelling and punctuation which I found to be useful after many years of studying US and UK English. In my country Liberia, we prefer US English to UK English; therefore, I have used US English in PERIOD 1.

REFERENCES

EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. Washington D.C: Euclid University Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.